

IMPROVING DRUG LOGISTICS MANAGEMENT AS A FACTOR FOR ENSURING NATIONAL DRUG SECURITY

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Relevance: drug safety is a key element of the national healthcare system, ensuring public access to quality medications. Currently, all existing logistics processes are characterized by various supply interruptions for vital medications, including frequent temperature violations due to storage conditions, high costs, and low supply chain transparency. The most global challenges, such as the pandemic and international supply chain disruptions, have included rising prices for transportation and various energy resources, increasing the risk and likelihood of drug shortages, especially in remote areas.

In such cases, to ensure sustainable supply, it has become necessary to improve logistics management, as well as implement various digital solutions to standardize these processes and integrate participants in the supply chain.

Purpose of the study: to develop and substantiate approaches to optimizing the management of drug supply chain logistics processes. These approaches will be aimed at improving the transparency and efficiency of these supply chains, as well as reducing and minimizing risks that could lead to disruptions in the quality and availability of drugs.

Materials and methods: the study utilized regulatory documents related to drug distribution, statistical data from the Ministry of Health, reports from pharmaceutical regulators, and various survey results from distributors and pharmacy chains. Comparative analyses of international and national sources were utilized, along with a SWOT analysis and case study analysis examining issues such as supply disruption monitoring, logistics risk assessment, and the development of an inventory model and management.

Results: the key challenges in drug logistics were identified, including a comprehensive shortage of modern warehouse space, temperature control issues, duplicate delivery cards, and high costs.

Proposals were formulated for the creation of a unified platform for tracking drug flows, as well as for demand forecasting, inventory management, and transportation and storage conditions.

Conclusions: improving drug logistics management is a key prerequisite for ensuring national security. The introduction of unified standards and personnel training can improve quality, availability, and safety, helping to address the issue of drug delivery to remote regions.

Governments and regulators always require requirements for the development and implementation of modern and relevant supply chain technologies.